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**To teach multiplication and division to elementary school students,
and to introduce its table cases.**

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***Abstract** – This article provides information on the stages of teaching multiplication and division to elementary school students, reinforcing them with problems and examples, and introducing them to table cases.*

***Keywords:** multiplication, division, multiplication tables, division tables, group counting, practical exercises, solving simple problems.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern education should be implemented in a way that increases the need for students to master the material more fully and more thoroughly, as well as to use independent thoughts in the lesson. In the course of the study, students should master the system of knowledge, skills and abilities of tabular multiplication. In order to achieve this result, such tasks that ensure the active participation of each student and increase the responsibility of students for the results of educational work should occupy a special place in the lesson.

In order to ensure a solid mastery of the multiplication table, it is necessary to organize the work of students in such a way that the calculation skills of table multiplication and division are qualitatively formed in elementary school students, they are conscious and from the table apart from using multiplication and division operations in different ways. The teacher can achieve this by using methods

and methods wisely. Acquaintance with the theoretical facts underlying the creation of a table of multiplication of schoolchildren only, a strict and consistent methodology will help to allocate time, and then to create tables and memorize them later.

Table multiplication and division are studied in the following sequence:

- 1) the specific meaning of multiplication;
- 2) the specific meaning of division;
- 3) commutative nature of multiplication;

A lot of preparation work is done before making the schedule. In it, the precise meaning of multiplication and division operations, their interrelationship, two types of division (by division and content) are studied in a generalized way. Pupils get acquainted with the substitution property of multiplication, finding the unknown component of multiplication and division operations, learn the necessary conversational material. All this makes it much easier to study the times table, freeing you from creating 4 tables and allowing you to limit yourself to only one. (Used to find all tabulated results of multiplication and division.)

The use of the permutation property of multiplication reduces the number of cases of tabular multiplication to be memorized in half. In multiplication, one number is repeatedly added as an addend to the unit of another number. In order to teach students how to multiply, they must first be taught to find the sum of the same divisors. These tasks are included in mathematics and subject practical education lessons. Group counting is widely used in practical activity classes. The teacher gives the following task: "Take two pieces of paper for Anwar Zakir and Shahla and distribute them. How many pieces of paper did you get?" Or: "Zakir, take one plasticine box for Shahla, Guli, and Shahnaz. How many plasticine boxes did you get in total?" Children group and list mosaic buttons, wooden constructor details, objects made in the lesson. In the school for hearing impaired children, such puzzles are performed in labor classes. (when making punched cards, lotto cards and cards). The following exercises are performed in mathematics classes.

1. Group counting Children learn to count by adding numbers of twos, threes and fours to the given number and count these groups starting from the given number. Exercises are performed on the basis of the following verbal tasks: "Count from 5 to 21 by 2", "Count by 2 from 10 to 4".
2. Creating examples based on practical work or the following tasks: "Take a rectangle 4 times out of 3. How many rectangles are there in total. Write and solve the example"

$$(3+3+3+3)=12;$$

Assignments are performed both orally and in writing. The following questions are asked to find out how the children understand these examples. "Why did you add the number three four times?"

Generalized questions are also asked: "Tell me, what did you do?"

3. Solving simple problems: "Zakir bought 4 notebooks. Each notebook costs 5 soums. How many soums did Zakir give for all the notebooks?". In such matters, the price of subjects is expressed to the students in a certain form:

Examining the relationships between the components and results of multiplication and division is an important step in students' learning of the multiplication table.

After studying the characteristics of multiplication and division, work on the table. It consists of multiplication by a constant multiplier, that is, 2 is multiplied by all the numbers of the natural series, then 3, and so on. In this case, the result of each subsequent multiplication is formed by the result that came before it. For example, in the multiplication table by 2, we find the result of 2×2 , and the next result is found by adding one more 2, that is, $4 + 2 = 6$. And in the constant multiplier table, a new situation is created every time (for example, $2 \times 4 = 2 + 2 + 2 + 2 = 8$, $3 \times 4 = 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 = 12$). This complicates the work.

From each case of multiplication, there is a new case of one multiplication and two cases of division. This greatly reduces the number of cases to remember in the following tables. For example, considering 2×8 , we can observe the cases of 8×2 , $26 \div 2$, and $16 \div 8$, and we create a table representation of multiplying 8 and dividing by 8. In short, in the process of teaching multiplication and division to elementary school students, we go from simple to complex, and practical examples are worked out to make it understandable to students. After mastering the basic concepts of multiplication and division, the table cases of multiplication and division are explained to children and the skill of using them in practice increases. Later, it is necessary for students to be able to use the tables of multiplication and division by heart and to be able to build them independently, reaching their original meaning.

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